

Background

Background: concisely explain the research area including references, and, where appropriate, relevant policy and practice developments or professional agendas

FoodSEqual Project 'Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities'

The Plymouth based work-package, for which this ethics application is pertinent, is part of a five year national consortium project led by the University of Reading (Prof Carol Wagstaff) and involves academics from Sussex, Kent and Cranfield Universities. It is funded (£6million) by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF) and runs from 1.2.21 until 31.1.26. (See Appendix ONE for summary of national project)

Project summary

The vision of the FoodSEqual project is to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse disadvantaged communities with choice and agency over the food they consume by co-developing new products, new supply chains and new policy frameworks that deliver affordable, attractive, healthy and sustainable diet. The recent COVID19 global pandemic has illustrated the fragility of the current UK food system. The failure of supply chains to operate, restrictions on social movement and reduction of employment opportunities was felt most extremely by disadvantaged communities. The number of adults who are food insecure in the Britain is estimated to have quadrupled under the COVID-19 lockdown (Loopstra 2020). Drawing together best practice from food system co-production methodologies, the FoodSEqual project will develop a community-informed approach to transform the food system to a model that benefits the environment, provides opportunities for small and large food businesses and gives access to culturally appropriate food for disadvantaged communities.

Plymouth context

More locally, Plymouth has pockets of serious social and economic deprivation, some of which are considered amongst the highest in England in terms of deprivation index (PCC, 2019a), with up to 10 years life expectancy difference between neighbourhoods. Of particular note, are high levels of child poverty (18.6% of Plymouth children) (PCC, 2019b) and increasing numbers of young people identified at risk of 'food insecurity' (Allerton et al 2019), the latter of which has been exacerbated by COVID, due to furlough, redundancy

and workless-ness. There are high levels of drug/alcohol addictions and mental health and disability issues across the city (PCC 2019b). Plymouth remains a low wage economy with many jobs of low stability (manufacturing/retail/hospitality), resulting in financial insecurity and recent unemployment levels being very high (e.g. 71% new benefit claimants in light of COVID) (PCC, 2021).

Aims and objectives

Aims and objectives: State what your study will achieve, key findings and any hypotheses. Include how you anticipate the fulfillment of the aims and key questions will move forward knowledge and where appropriate, policy or practice

Aim of the Plymouth work-package:

Co-production of food systems for disadvantaged communities in Plymouth to support the national **FoodSEqual** project deliverables and development of co-production methodologies and community food researcher model.

Objectives:

- A. Carry out benchmarking activities (e.g. foodscape mapping; 'foodways' survey/interviews) and a scoping review to assess the diets of disadvantaged communities in the UK (informed by local Plymouth consultations)
- B. Recruit and work closely with a diverse sample of 'disadvantaged communities' across Plymouth using already existing community networks, brokered by Food Plymouth CIC (the local sustainable food places partnership) and other local organisations already working with these communities
- C. Set up and implement a group of Plymouth community food researchers to support data collection and co-production methodologies locally
- D. Establish innovative qualitative and participatory action methods that enable community knowledge to be valued and shared reciprocally (locally and nationally)
- E. To carry out ongoing creative research activities that meet the needs of the national project deliverables, tailored to the needs of local communities, eg setting up a 'citizens jury' to support ongoing project research co-developments
- F. Ongoing collaboration, dissemination and public engagement events to share progress/learning of the project locally, regionally and nationally

This ethics application is pertinent to **PHASE one** of the Plymouth work-package which runs from approx. May to December 2021 (see Appendix TWO - gaant chart). Further ethical applications will be needed for subsequent phases of the project as they unfold.

Methods

Methods: explain how participants will be recruited (where, by whom, how many; inclusion and exclusion criteria), what data will be collected, how it will be analysed (statistical tests, sample size considerations). This should include references of the particular methodology being used; how it will be employed in relation to this study; which techniques of analysis will be used once data are collected and how this will be applied to the particular data set.

The complex nature of decisions about food is constrained by both physical access (Lang et al 2001) and choice (FAO, 2009) and therefore innovative co-production and Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodologies will be used across this 5 year project. Initially, we will engage disadvantaged community groups, but in the longer run we will also engage volunteers, businesses and civic organisations that inform food policy, to get a robust picture of the complexity and interdependence of various factors, so that we can build a transformative framework for food system change.

Methods to be used in the Plymouth work-package are presently outlined in alignment with the objectives:

A. **SCOPING REVIEW** (and other benchmarking)

A scoping review will be carried out to appraise what is known about the diets of disadvantaged communities in the UK. This review will employ the six-stage framework developed by Arskey & O'Malley (2005) expanded upon by Levac, Colquhoun & O'Brien (2010). Most of this review is desk based thus no ethical approval required. But the final phase will involve consultations with community participants. Once evidence (published and grey literature) has been appraised, two creative interactive community workshops (see methodological section below) will be run to share, in an accessible manner, a summary of the findings. Community members will be invited to respond and share their views on some of the topics identified. Questions asked will include those current being developed for the scoping review (see Appendix THREE for draft outline of scoping review)

Other benchmarking activities will include:

- i) 'Mapping local foodscape' – as per scoping review, this will be mainly desk based/observational work. But once ethical approval is granted, some of the evidence gathered via the mapping exercise will be used to support creative community mapping workshops with community participants, to enable

knowledge exchange about the evidence (see methodological section below) to support ongoing food systems conversations with our target communities

- ii) 'Foodways' survey/interview - Co-production of cross-sectional 'survey/interview' by community research team (with community/business participants using adapted existing validated questionnaire tools (see methodological section below)

B. RECRUITMENT

Initial recruitment of 'gatekeepers'

The Plymouth Principal Investigator (PI) already has a strong local network in place (from previous research), by which to access a diverse sample of disadvantaged communities. Those already written into the bid include: Provide Devon (Partner A) – a charity offering emergency food aid to families in Plymouth via referral agencies and The Plymouth Soup Run (Partner B) – offering emergency food aid to individuals with complex lives. Further partners have verbally agreed via the Plymouth Complex Lives Alliance (e.g. Shekinah; Hamoaze House). Discussions are underway with active community regeneration projects in areas of high deprivation e.g. the Four Greens Community Trust (north Plymouth) and Whitleigh Big Local, as well as early conversations with housing associations, to ensure this project has strong links with a range of suitable gatekeepers to access appropriate participants. So far, all have agreed a strong interest in this project. **Gatekeeper information sheets will be provided to all partners to ensure a firm understanding of the project methods (See Appendix 2.5) including data protection.** As the project develops, more partners deemed appropriate will need to be brought on board as gatekeepers, for example, local food businesses, suppliers and producers to continue this dynamic multi-stage recruitment process (Palinkas et al 2015).

Recruitment of disadvantaged communities

The Plymouth work-package project aims to recruit approx. 200 individuals from disadvantaged communities to engage in this project. Additional smaller 'sub-samples' may also be recruited (e.g. n=25), depending on the activities decided via our co-production methodologies. Although a stable sample is desirable for the five year duration of the project, acknowledgement is given to the often transient nature of disadvantaged communities with complex lives, meaning that the sample may change as the project

progresses. But given the complexity and variety of project methodologies and associated activities, the more individuals we can recruit the better to avoid sampling/research fatigue.

Convenience and purposive sampling will initially be used, accessing relevant individuals via gatekeepers (Namageyo-Funa et al, 2014), consisting of community stakeholders who are actively involved in working with disadvantaged communities (see section above). To meet our aim of diverse sampling, we intend to have representation from adults with families, children and teenagers, as well as individuals who are not part of family groups. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are outlined below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Single adults males/females/non-binary (over 18years) engaging with community services/gatekeepers
- Adults with families identified by community gatekeeper
- Teenagers/youth accessing relevant youth services/gatekeepers
- Children – accessed via schools/community gatekeepers
- Sufficient English to communicate verbally (or interpreter may be used if English not first language)
- Ability to participate in creative methods
- Access to online platforms (initially) to engage with activities

Exclusion Criteria

There will be a requirement to assess at the time of recruitment, or in any one given session, and exclude as deemed appropriate (assistance will be gained from gatekeepers):

- Those demonstrating signs of being ‘heavily under the influence’ or ‘visibly unable to communicate’*
- Those who pose a risk to themselves or others through manifestations of mental health problems or the influence of non-prescriptions drugs and/or alcohol**.

*Any individual excluded on these grounds, will be given the opportunity to participate in a subsequent session, as deemed appropriate

**As regards mental health, there may be participants with defined mental health problems that are relatively well managed with medication.

C. SETTING UP COMMUNITY FOOD RESEARCHER TEAM

Community food researcher model for co-production

In Plymouth, one of the main elements to be implemented is the setting up of a Community Food Researcher Team. We will be looking to Whitley, Reading as an exemplar for this, as they already have a well-established community research team in place (Lloyd-Evans 2020) which has successfully showcased PAR in action towards engaging communities in co-producing their own knowledge to engender social action towards community improvement

and social justice. Community Researcher Team Development will take place through a workshop/online platform for sharing best practice, recruitment, ethics, fieldwork safety, training and safeguarding between the four communities

The newly appointed Plymouth research team members (Research Fellow, Community Research team manager and soon to be appointed Community Research Liaison officers) will support the planning and set up of a team of community food researchers, who will each play a key role within the recruited communities to support co-production methodological processes and data collection. The PI and Research Fellow have undergone training on the ethical conduct of research, the content of which will be adapted when we train the community research team. Food Plymouth CIC is sub-contracted to provide services around recruiting, training, supervising, supporting and managing this small team of freelance community researchers and will be supported in research skills by our academic research team.

D. Establishing innovative qualitative and participatory action methods and E Ongoing recruitment, co-production and creative research activities

PAR training workshops

Once the community research team is in place, we will run a series of national multi-stakeholder Participatory Action Research (PAR) training workshops which will involve all four communities (Plymouth, Tower Hamlets, Brighton and Hove and Whitley, Reading), civil society organisations, partners and businesses with a focus on creative, digital and art of conversation methods (see below for examples), adaptation of methods to meet any social distancing requirements associated with Covid19 and tackling the digital divide. PAR workshops will co-produce a standardised methodological framework for all partners across the national project and will inform the Plymouth work-package, to enable a series of ongoing creative local activities to promote engagement, map local foodscapes, community experiences and capabilities. PAR methods are well documented for improving the situations of vulnerable people (Crane and O-Regan, 2010). Such empowerment driven person- and community-centred approaches are known to improve wellbeing (Wood et al 2016) and engagement.

PAR Methodological approaches

The Plymouth PI already has a strong track record of delivering successful PAR methods using photo elicitation (Pettinger et al 2017) and is very sensitive to the needs of ethics, emotion and power dynamics of PAR methodologies (Pettinger et al 2018) and is confident to evolve and adapt as necessary the use of creative methods to engage disadvantaged

communities via participatory food events which can also act as collaborative public engagement opportunities (Pettinger et al 2019).

This research will incorporate the broadest holistic socio-cultural role of food in participants' lives and other determining factors influencing food choices. Participatory field work activities will also co-create research with food retailers, suppliers and producers, who will be recruited at a later phase. Our co-developed PAR will capture the food, health and environmental aspirations amongst disadvantaged consumers and the broader foodscapes in which they exist (eg preferences for/barriers to UK sourcing, sustainable packaging, seasonality of ingredients and farming/businesses that could supply them). We will be using a range of methodological approaches in Plymouth to engage our target communities for data collection purposes, with the support of the community researcher team. Our approaches will be tailored to the needs of the particular 'life-cycle' stage of participants (ie may be modified for younger audiences), and will include the following types of methods:

- i. Initial consultations [Semi-structured (audio) interviews] to assess the diets of disadvantaged communities (to include adapted Appreciative Inquiry (AI) method) with key gatekeepers, recruiting up to 8 stakeholders from each partner organisation and community members (n=6 identified community champions). The AI method presents an alternative to the problem-solving approach underpinning action research and offers an affirmative approach for evaluating and envisioning future initiatives based on optimisation of best practice (Bellinger & Elliot, 2011), emphasising the power of capacity, problem solving and resourcefulness. Questions will be formed in response to the scoping review findings, and will be based around socio-cultural food preferences, shopping patterns, attitudes (food and system), growing, knowledge acquisition, emergency food use/food insecurity parameters. We will include aspirations for as well as barriers to healthy/sustainable eating: e.g. food affordability, accessibility, control over ethical choices etc.
- ii. Mapping and observations – these will be an ongoing activities throughout the 5 year project. The local foodscape will be observed and mapped by the researchers, community research teams and community participants, to provide an overview of food related experiences, activities and assets within communities focussing on public health, social justice and sustainability (Vonthron et al 2020). Photography and film will be a key part of the observations, to document project progress. Creative community workshops will be run at various points in our time-line to

ensure that community members are able to respond and feed in to our mapping outputs (see vi below)

- iii. Focus groups – will be used at key points in the project as a way of ascertaining participants' experiences of food and the food system. We may run up to 10 separate focus groups throughout the five years. Focus groups are an appropriate method of data collection because they enable a focussed group discussion and produce large amounts of concentrated data in a short period of time (Morgan 1998). The advantage of focus groups over interviews is group discussion but they will require good facilitation to ensure that valuable insights are not lost because of a dominant group member. The project lead (CP) and research fellow (LH) and possibly community research team leads will co-facilitate these groups. All focus groups will be audio-recorded for transcription purposes.

The facilitators will create a suitable environment that encourages freedom of discussion, aiming to create focus groups where participants are likely to be comfortable with one another. At the start of each focus group, clear ground-rules will be set and participants will be reminded that a supportive environment can often lead to 'over-disclosure' thus compromising confidentiality. Equally the group dynamics will be managed to ensure all have the opportunity to speak if they wish to and no group member is allowed to dominate the group. A purposive sample of between 6-12 people will be sought (Green and Thorogood, 2014, p130) for each focus group with the aim of recruiting 8 participants per focus group.

- iv. Co-produced 'foodways' (oral) Survey/interview (see Appendix FOUR) Co-production of cross-sectional 'survey/interview' by research teams with community/business participants using adapted existing validated questionnaire tools. We cannot share a final version of the tool to be used because it will be decided by the community participants themselves, in line with co-production philosophies. However, initial researcher input will include sources such as 'Healthy eating index'(Pot et al 2014); Characteristics of sustainable/healthy diet (Gonzales-Fischer & Garnett 2016) to capture preferences, patterns, choices, attitudes (food and system), shopping, growing, knowledge acquisition, emergency food use/food insecurity parameters. We will include barriers to healthy/sustainable eating: e.g. food affordability, accessibility, control over choice, sensory preferences, cognitive biases. This tool will initially be drafted between University of Plymouth and University of Reading academics and then shared via learning workshops with

communities around survey co-design, piloting and delivery as well as validation of survey/interview tool.

The survey/interview tool is intended to be used with a sample >100 participants per each of the four communities (Plymouth being one) and cover a spectrum of ages, family structures and cultures in each region, enabling (a) comparison of diets to the national 'benchmarking' picture and (b) development of a rich understanding of the range and variability of diet and dietary drivers in each community. See appendix 3 for benchmarking survey draft ideas, which will be co-designed further as community research teams are set up.

- v. Photo-elicitation – to explore food practices and experiences of a sub-sample of (n=12 participants). Participants will photograph their food activities throughout each day for one week, using a modified 'Photo-Voice' method. Rooted in ethnographic observation, this has successfully built skills in disadvantaged communities (Wang et al 2000). Food experiences and reflections on the method will be explored using a focus group (Pettinger et al 2017). This will support the photographic data and provide meanings contextualised from their own perspectives and on their terms (Liamputtong 2007). The photographs will inform semi-structured interview and/or focus group discussions (above) and other creative public engagement activities e.g. exhibitions, citizens juries (see vii).

- vi. Participatory Food events (as outlined in Pettinger et al 2019) to engage large groups of community participants (n=20-30). These events will enable knowledge exchange around the socio-cultural determinants of food and the food system, participatory creative methods will be used as a vehicle to discuss and debate topical food issues to create a transformative vision for the future of food. A range of well-established participatory arts based/creative methods will be used including cooking; collage or zining; quizzes and games; story telling (Pettinger et al 2019; Wheeler 2018; Flint et al, 2017). Such creative methods can provide an important space for our participants to generate meaningful narratives. These narratives form the basis of future research that taps into their potential to be transformative, whereby food (activities) then become a powerful catalyst to re-connect people culturally and socially. These creative methods, therefore, present an important academic contribution to methodological landscapes, as well as offering, more broadly, a way of understanding our food culture and social world.

- vii. A citizen panel/jury will be set up in phase one (and will be developed through subsequent phases) (Wakeford, 2002). Aiming for up to n=8 community members for this purpose (recruited via gatekeepers and other creative food activities). This is group of community led 'non-specialists', to support and steer the Plymouth work-package as it progresses. Monetary incentives will be given to panel members, as this vital role this will help to validate the community processes adopted, and can act to hold the powerful to account – this process needs to be fair, representative and transparent.

Data Analyses:

Will vary depending on the method being employed. Most data will be qualitative, apart from the 'foodways' survey/interviews, which will include quantitative data. These data will be analysed appropriately using SPSS and relevant statistical tests run alongside academic partners in Reading and Sussex (as these are agreed – Academics in Reading are leading the quantitative element of this research)

A reflexive approach will be adopted by the lead researchers (Denscombe, 2010) and will be encouraged in the community food researcher teams, which will permit ongoing thematic analyses to be iteratively carried out. Similarly, using 'Constant comparative analysis' (Hewitt-Taylor 2001), which analyses multiple methods concurrently, consultations, focus group transcripts and photographs can be coded, then categories and themes developed and interpreted by the research team members. Analysis will be on going, using qualitative data packages, such as Nvivo10 (2011). Analyses aim be as faithful as possible to any respondents' accounts. In terms of triangulation, all observations and field notes will be kept as these are recommended, particularly for non-verbal communications (Fade, 2004). Following transcription participants will also be given the opportunity to check the contents of the transcript (Porter, 2008). The research team will be reflexive in understanding their role in interpreting findings and they will endeavour to act in a way so as not to exaggerate any potential power imbalance (Liamputtong, 2007). Further authentication of analyses will take place using the 'Voice Centred Relational Methods' (VCRM) (Mauthner and Doucet 1998) will generate themes from interview/focus group transcripts for interpretation by the multi-disciplinary research team. In the spirit of co-production the significance of all themes generated will be discussed/appraised by the research team and participants.

Participatory analyses

In the true nature of PAR (Pettinger et al 2018) and co-production methodologies, we will try as far as possible to engage participants in all stages of the research processes, including analyses. This means exploring the option of participation in data analyses (Nind, 2011) which may include sharing discussions around themes to inform project progression and/or outcomes. We acknowledge the potential challenges this might present and will mitigate these as the project unfolds.

The data and dialogues outlined in the first phase of the work will identify the exemplar foods/products that will be used in the 'innovation' phase of work (phase two – not covered in this ethics form – as this will be covered by University of Reading ethics)

Anticipated findings and their relevance

Anticipated findings and their relevance

This Plymouth work package will be used to inform the national consortium project, using tailored innovative creative methods to inform the overall objectives and deliverables. This project will focus on working closely with disadvantaged communities, who are often forgotten voices in this arena, to jointly imagine new solutions to address a lack of access to healthy, sustainable food. The project will unite researchers and food industry representatives with charity leaders to reimagine how food policy, products and supply chains can be co-developed.

The project will use innovative (bottom-up) 'co-production' approaches, effectively putting communities at the heart of the work by setting up an active 'Community Food Researcher' team in Plymouth which will support the research processes and data collection.

It will develop a framework to ensure food is affordable, desirable and fits with the complex demands on people's lives. This means regular consumption of a nutritious diet, produced in a way that is good for our planet, will be an attainable aspiration for all members of our society.

Ethical aspects of research

Please indicate how you will ensure this research conforms to each clause of the University of Plymouth's [Principles for Research Involving Human Participants](#). Please address each of the ethical principles set out below

Informed consent

Consent will firstly be secured by gatekeeper/partner organisations, (using tailored participant information sheets) so that access to sample can then be supported.

To protect the welfare of research participants the nature of the study will be clearly explained via an information sheet (Appendix FIVE). In keeping with best practice the researcher will also meet with participants to explain the study (National Research Ethics Service (NRES), 2011). If a participant cannot read, the information sheet can be read out like a script (NRES, 2011). Informed written consent will be sought from all participants in relation to all participatory methods (see appendix SIX for copies of consent forms).

As outlined above, if a participant cannot read, the information sheet can be read out like a script (NRES, 2011). If a participant is unable to provide consent for other reasons (such as substance or alcohol ingestion) then they will not be able to participate (see inclusion/exclusion criteria). If this does occur, there may be chance for a subsequent research activity to be attended instead (depending on timeframe). Gatekeepers (who have already provided consent) may also need to be present for communication purposes where necessary.

Due to covid there is a good chance that some of our initial activities will need to be carried out online rather than in person. We will be using opt in/opt out functions via our digital platforms, and information sheets will be made available to participants in advance and consent forms will be included for use via the JISC online survey system, so that participants will have the option to consent at the time of the online meeting, or before. Gatekeepers will be present where possible to support participants wellbeing

Equality and diversity

We have a strong and credible 'gatekeeper network' already in place for access to a diverse community sample, having well established ongoing relationships with organisations serving vulnerable and disadvantaged communities. We will endeavour to recruit a diverse sample drawing from often under-represented community groups, such as adults who are unemployed, adults with disabilities, adults with children, and other minority groups who are particularly at risk of food insecurity.

At the heart of our project proposal is the belief that a right to food is the right to dignity. We deeply acknowledge the need for non-judgement, sensitivity & inclusion when working with often vulnerable disadvantaged communities to combat stigma. Our ethos is to offer inclusive, holistic, safe (fun/creative) food research activities for communities to engage with. Feeding emotional, spiritual and socio-cultural is as important as nutritional/physical aspects.

We will support participants with incentives for engagement to include any travel/time reimbursement. We feel this is vital to support our community groups. We will only request relevant (GDPR compliant) personal data from participants that falls within the equality and diversity agenda.

Openness and honesty

It will be important to make it clear to any participants in the study that anything they say will be confidential and will not affect future care or support they receive. Participants will be informed before taking part in the study that if they divulge information during any of the participatory methods that is demonstrating harm to others confidentiality may need to be breached. Following transcription of qualitative aspects, participants will be given the opportunity to check the contents of their transcript and feed into analyses (part of co-production methods).

Payment of participants

Due to the nature of our 'co-production' methodologies, and the setting up of a Community Food Researcher team to support this, we will need to consider carefully the appropriate and ethical remuneration of our research participants. This is already an ongoing topic of discussion with the national research consortium and agenda item for discussion/review at our management board meetings.

We appreciate the need for stringent auditing of research expenses especially for community groups and charities (our sub-contractors). We have already discussed with Food Plymouth CIC (our sub-contractor for the Community Food Researcher team) the need for transparent monitoring of any expenses and/or remuneration of research participants. The research team will also be keeping our own records for this purpose and will also have access to our sub-contractors records, in case of an audit. We will be keeping a simple password protected spreadsheet with date, spend, reasons, recipient plus copies of all receipts (any out of pocket expenses e.g. child care costs, travel expenses and subsistence). This is in line with the University of Plymouth's 'Expenses and benefits for employees' document, section 11, p 6 and has been discussed with HR and Occupational Health.

Deception

Not being used

Right to withdraw

Participation will be voluntary, and individuals will be informed of their right to withdraw at any point during the study, without reprisal. Should participants choose to withdraw during the study, we will endeavour to remove their data from analysis, although there may be

occasion where this is not possible. For example if they withdraw from a focus group or other recorded group activity after the data collection has started, the data collected up to that point will be retained. This is because, as it is a group discussion, the sense of the data will be lost. None of that participant's words will be used in the reporting of the data.

Protection from harm

Children/young people; vulnerable adults; sensitive topics; permission of gatekeeper

Vulnerability - It may be that some participants find it distressing talking about their food experiences. The researcher or research fellow will be mindful of this and will ensure that if participants do become distressed they can be referred on for appropriate support. The focus group(s) or other creative research activity will also be terminated if necessary. All interviews and focus groups will take place in an appropriately safe environment for the participants needs, and where necessary lone working policies will be followed. Key gatekeepers, support workers and volunteers will be informed of participants involvement as a routine precaution.

The researchers acknowledge that working with vulnerable and disadvantaged communities will present certain challenges such as requirement for empathy and diplomacy around sensitive topics within the remit of the research. Most of the research team members already have direct practitioner experience working with vulnerable groups. The team will, nonetheless, be actively involved in regular communications with the various community gatekeepers and their support teams, who have a wealth of experience on the sensitivities involved in working within this area.

Debrief

As participants will be made fully aware of the purpose of the research there is no formal requirement for debriefing, however in the true nature of PAR co-production methodologies, the research team will endeavour to include ongoing debriefing throughout the various stages of the project. Community Research team will offer support and de-brief sessions following each different methodological approach to check progress. The researcher will ask participants at the end of the interviews/focus group(s) if they have any worries about what has been said and check that they are feeling alright before they leave. Appropriate support and advice will be offered if necessary. Each year of the project will run participatory events, such as peoples/citizens assemblies, which will provide opportunities for participants to anonymously feed into the next stage of the project. This will be facilitated via our citizens jury group

Dissemination

Participants are informed and will give consent that their data can be used for dissemination purpose, eg reports, publications and conferences presentations. Also possible use of creative outputs (eg. photographs, collage, film?) for exhibitions and other participatory events, with consent being sought for this.

Anonymity

Data will not be reported specifically at the individual level, so anonymity will be maintained. Some creative methods (eg photographs) may have potential to reveal identities.

Participants will be given the option of giving consent for all, some or none of their creative outputs to be used in dissemination. It is possible that individuals may not remain anonymous if they consent to allowing photographs/outputs to be published. The researcher will discuss with participants the possible implications of this. It is envisaged that an exhibition of photographs and other creative outputs may form part of the dissemination. All participants will be consulted about confidentiality/anonymity regarding any public exhibition of photographs/other creative outputs

Confidentiality

All participants' personal details will remain confidential and anonymous - with pseudonyms being used during write-ups or other dissemination. No one apart from the research team will have access to the consent forms. This will be the only documentation to contain the names of the participants. No one apart from the research team will have access to the data/consent forms. Any observational notes, photos and documents will be coded and stored systematically in an electronic password protected format using a PC/laptop (GDPR compliant). Audio files and transcripts will be anonymised and will be stored electronically in the same manner as outlined above (any hard copies will be stored in a lockable filing cabinet in the RF office, PAHC to ensure that confidentiality is not breached).

Participants will be informed that all data will be kept for a minimum of 10 years. Data on any computer used for transcribing and analysis will be stored in a password-secured and encrypted folder and access restricted to the research team. The audio files will be destroyed at the end of the study and all data including transcripts will be stored for a minimum of 10 years (as per Plymouth University policy). The study will comply with the Data Protection Act (Great Britain. GDPR Protection Act 2018).

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